

Influence Receipt of ZISWAF Funds, ROA, and Wadiah Bonus against CAR with Firm Size as Variable Moderation Period Year 2015.Q1 – Year 2023.Q3

Ahmad Auly Ahady
Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia
Aulyahady@gmail.com

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine how the acceptance of ziswaf funds, ROA, and wadiah bonus affect CAR with Firm size as a moderating variable. This study uses Islamic bank financial journals from 2018 to 2023. For five years, the purposive sample consisted of 115 samples. Panel Data Regression Analysis and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) were used, all using Eviews 12. The results showed that ziswaf fund receipts had a large negative impact on CAR in the banking industry from 2018 to 2023. Firm size cannot control the effect of ziswaf fund receipts, ROA, and wadiah bonus on Islamic banking CAR during the period 2018-2023. In order for the research results to represent different banking sectors, future research is expected to use additional moderating variables. In addition, it is expected to use bank samples from various types of banking

Keywords: Ziswaf Fund, ROA, Wadiah Bonus, Firm Size, CAR

INTRODUCTION

Islamic banking is developing fast. After a number of crisis economy, sharia banking gets more attention big. Crisis the world economy in question is crisis 1998 and 2009. Second crisis This impact large in countries in the Asian region, including Indonesia. A field study conducted in Amman, Jordan for two years (2007-2009), found that crisis more global economy Lots impact negative at conventional banks than Syariah banking.. This matter can achieved Because Islamic principles make method investment This more moral and less risky compared to with conventional banks. Scenario has open room more acceptance Good to Islamic finance in general and Islamic banking in particular and provides alternative to conventional (Sari et al., 2020) .

ZISWAF funds (Zakat, Infaq, Alms, and Waqf) are funds collected from various sources, incl individuals and organizations, for Then used in various related activities with interest social and economic public. ZISWAF has objective For increase well-being society, especially for those who need it most, as well For increase trust public to zakat amil institution. In the implementation of management of ZISWAF funds, amil yap institutions play a role as managers and those who don't need answer For collect, manage, and allocate these funds. Institutions can form institutions established by the government and established institutions in a way self-help by the Community (Handayani, 2020) .

One study use mark asset net (ROA) as variable moderation For determine How policy dividend impact on value companies in the sector banking conventional. Study the show that mark asset net (ROA) affects mark company in a way significant, and policy dividend No can moderate connection between ROA and value company. In addition, ROA has used as variable moderation in influence capital structure against mark company at level (Permatasari et al., 2019) .

Size the company is very influential disclosure of Islamic Social Reporting (ISR) in sharia commercial banks. Research conducted use method study statistics and analysis panel data regression shows that size company (size company) has an impact on ISR reporting of Islamic banks in Indonesia. Size company defined as total assets companies, and findings study show that Islamic banks with more total assets big will influence IS disclosure. AAOIFI (Accounting and Auditing Organization for Islamic Financial Institutions) created ISR index, which is reject measuring implementation performance social Syariah banking. Index This consists from a number indicator CSR standards.. Study others also show that size company, capital adequacy, risk financing, and stability company to The profitability of Islamic banks in Indonesia can also be achieved measured and analyzed (Baiquni, 2017) .

Collection of Zakat and Waqf funds (ZISWAF), one of them source of funds that refers to principles wadiah guaranteed by law and MUI fatwa, has an impact positive on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of sharia banks. These funds can used For launch product new, like mudharabah, so increase Islamic bank income. Return assets (ROA) also has an effect positive against CAR. ROA is size calculated profit from total income divided with total assets. Sharia bank with high ROA will own more performance good and have ability For increase CAR. Wadiah bonuses also have an impact positive against CAR. Prize bonus is part from Sharia bank income received by customers. If it's a gift bonus high, then Islamic banks will own more performance well, which in turn will CAR will increase (Helena Purba & Marjulin, 2022) .

Research purposes is For research How receipt of Zakat, Waqf and Sadaqah (ZISWAF) funds as well as Return on Assets (ROA) and Wadiah Bonuses have an impact to the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) in Islamic banking in Indonesia. Study this will too use firm size as variable moderation in period 2015.Q1 to in 2023.Q3.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Ziswaf Funds (zakat, infaq, alms, waqf)

Zakat is treasure in amount certain issues are issued the owner as cleaner himself and his property from everything that pollutes it, as well expect the blessing of Allah SWT. Zakat is also a effort For realize mark concern social in life real. The basic word (masdar) from the word zakat comes from from the word zaka, which means growing, holy, blessing, and developing. Infaq originate from the word nafaqa, which means " to have passing, passing, or finished. However, infaq means give part treasure to others for free. Therefore that's it, infaq is donate, give sustenance, or spend something to others for help they fulfil need them, like food and drink, with sincere and only because of Allah SWT. By etymology, " almsgiving " comes from from the word " shadaqohyang ", which means something a gift given by someone to other people spontaneous and voluntary without limited in time or amount. By terminology, alms interpreted as giving somebody to the right person accept it in a way sincere with hope only blessings of Allah SWT (Wulpiah, 2017) .

Return on Assets

Investors and analysts finance often using return on assets (ROA), as ratio finances used For measure how much effective something company in produce profit from each unit of asset it owns. By simple, ROA can be calculated with share profit clean company with the total value of the assets it owns. Asset value (ROA) can be helps investors and analysts finance evaluate efficiency company in produce profit. Second, ROA can be help company in find assets that do not productive or No efficient in produce profit. However, ROA also has a number of weakness. Firstly, ROA does not take into account factor risk in produce profit, and secondly, ROA does not take into account difference in company capital structure. In interpreting ROCE, ROA does not take into account factors. Return

Return On Assets (ROA) or ratio return on total assets is one of form from ratio profitability. Ratio profitability is ability company For obtain profit from his business (Sunyoto, 2013). Following is formula For looking for return on assets

$$\text{ROA} = (\text{Net Income} : \text{Total Assets}) \times 100\%$$

Prize bonus

Prize bonus is a bonus given as incentive to custodian of wadiah funds, which is product from institution Islamic finance. Prize bonus can in the form of cash and distributed to account custodian of wadiah funds. Writing " wadiah " in context This originate from the word " trust " which means trust or obligation For regulate and mandate party funds third For channeled, esp from savings. Prize bonus can in the form of a top bonus balance lowest, top bonus base daily average balance, or top bonus base balance daily Giving gift bonuses done with objective increase awareness customers to importance save and invest in sharia banks. Prize bonuses are also available increase trust customers towards Islamic banks and improve faithfulness customers in save and invest in sharia banks. In synthesis, gift bonuses is something form incentives provided to customers as rewards on their savings do it at a sharia bank. Giving gift bonuses done with objective increase awareness customers to importance save and invest in Islamic banks and increase trust customers towards Islamic banks (Sardiana & Zulfison, 2016) .

Capital adequacy ratio

The Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is something ratio used For evaluate ability a deep bank withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance. CAR is calculated with method divide total bank capital by total assets at risk, then multiplied with 100% for get percentage. In CAR, Tier 1 Capital consists on share ordinary and profitable detained, which is considered as highest capital quality Because can withhold loss without causing the bank to become insolvent. Tier 2 Capital consists of on debts that are not guaranteed and instrument other, which is considered not enough reliable However can withhold loss part small. CAR is used as yardstick measuring strength bank finances and capabilities withhold loss. The more high CAR, then the bank is considered own more abilities Good in withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance. CAR is also used as test stress For many banks, for determine How many a lot of money the bank needs to face various risks on various sectors and fronts faced. CAR is also used as standard For determine does the bank have Enough capital For withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance. CAR is regulated by the Central Bank and varies by country. In Indonesia, commercial banks must has a CAR of at least 9% In synthesis, the CAR is something important ratio For evaluate deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance. CAR is used as yardstick measuring strength bank finance and use as standard For determine does the bank have Enough capital For withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance (Sofyan, 2021) .

Following is formula For look for the capital adequacy ratio

$$\text{CAR} = (\text{Tier 1 Capital} + \text{Tier 2 Capital}) / \text{Risk-Weighted Assets}$$

Firm size

The definition of Firm Size is something size, scale, or describing variables big or small company based on a number of terms, such as total assets, log size, market value, shares, total sales, total income, total capital, etc. Firm size available be measured with various mark such as total assets, amount sales, average sales, and total assets. Size company This used For represent characteristics finance company, like ability company in access financial resources, capabilities company in produce income, etc. (Luly, 2020) .

Influence receipt of ziswaf funds with Capital Adequacy ratio (H1)

Influence ZISWAF Fund Receipts to Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) are something purposeful research For test How ZISWAF funds can be received influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance. Study This using secondary data

from report Islamic banking finance and uses approach quantitative For analyze influence of ZISWAF funds on CAR. Research result show that receipt of ZISWAF funds is not own influence significant against CAR. This matter because Islamic banking is in use of more capital be careful and focused guard bank liquidity, so No there is influence significant against CAR a approach efficiency and success economy company can used For determine connection between receipt of zakat funds (Zakat) and Return on Assets (ROA) (Muharramah, 2017) .

Effect of Return on assets with *capital adequacy ratio* (H2)

The effect of Return on Assets (ROA) on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is something purposeful research For test how ROA can be influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance. ROA is calculated with method share profit clean with total assets owned by the bank, then multiplied with 100% for get percentage. Research result show that ROA has influence positive and significant against CAR. The more high ROA, then the more high CAR. ROA can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increasing CAR (Ruri Kurniasari, 2022) .

Effect of Wadiah Bonus with *Capital adequacy ratio* (H3)

The effect of the Wadiah Bonus on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is something purposeful research For test how about wadiah bonus can influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance. Prize bonus is something form incentives provided to customers as rewards on their savings do it at a sharia bank. Research result show that gift bonus own influence positive against CAR. Prize bonus can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increasing CAR (Zumara, 2021) .

Influence Receipt of Ziswaf funds on the Capital adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size (H4)

Influence Acceptance of ZISWAF Funds towards Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is moderated with Firm Size is something purposeful research For test How ZISWAF funds can be received influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance, as well How size company can influence influence the. Research result show that ZISWAF fund receipts have influence positive against CAR, however influence the can vary depending on size company. ZISWAF funds can be received increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR. However, size company can influence influence the with method reduce deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can reducing CAR (Hayunah, 2018) .

The influence of Return on assets on the capital adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size (H5)

The influence of Return On Assets (ROA) on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is moderated with Firm Size is something purposeful research For test how ROA can be influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance, as well How size company can influence influence the. Research result show that ROA has influence positive against CAR, however influence the can vary depending on size company. ROA can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR. However, size company can influence influence the with method reduce deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can reducing CAR (Novrianti, 2021) .

The effect of the Wadiah Bonus on The capita adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size (H6)

The influence of the Wadiah Bonus on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) is moderated with Firm Size is something purposeful research For test how about wadiah

bonus can influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance, as well How size company can influence influence the. Research result show that gift bonus own influence positive against CAR, however influence the can vary depending on size company. Prize bonus can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR. However, size company can influence influence the with method reduce deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can reducing CAR (Mulyadhi, 2020) .

Influence receipt of ziswaf funds, return on assets, and wadiah bonuses on capital adequacy ratio (H7)

Influence ZISWAF Fund Receipts, Return On Assets (ROA), and Wadiah Bonus to Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) are something purposeful research For test How receipt of ZISWAF funds, ROA, and wadiah bonuses can influence deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finance. Research result show that receipt of ZISWAF funds is not influential significant against CAR. ROA has influence positive against CAR, however influence the can vary depending on size company. Prize bonus own influence positive against CAR, however influence the can vary depending on the size of the company (Khusnul Imamah & Achmad Munif, 2018) .

Following is connection between variable independent with variable dependent

Figure 1:
Framework conceptual

Research methods

Method used in study This is method quantitative. Data used in study This is secondary data that comes from from report accessed annually via the Financial Services Authority website. Population used is company sector finance in 2015.Q1 – 2023 which is listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (BEI) with technique taking sample use purposive sampling technique (Novianto, 2021) .

Data analysis methods used in research This are Panel Data Regression Model and Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA). Test interactions or often called with Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA) using approach sustaining analytics integrity sample and deliver base For give influence moderator variable (Kusnadi & Tandika, 2019) .

Following is inner model equations analysis panel data regression:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e_i$$

Where:

Y = Capital adequacy ratio

α = constant

β = Coefficient Regression

X₁ = Receipt of Ziswaf Funds

X₂ = Return on assets

X₃ = Gift bonus

e_i = Error

Testing hypothesis in research This use analysis regression with variable moderation Moderating Regression Analysis (MRA), eq the regression contain element interaction with formula equality as following

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 Z + \beta_5 X_1 * Z + \beta_6 X_2 * Z + \beta_7 X_3 * Z + e_i$$

Where: Y = Capital adequacy ratio

α = Constant

β = Coefficient Regression

X₁ = Receipt of Ziswaf Funds

X₂ = Return on assets

X₃ = Gift bonus

Z = Firm Size

X₁*Z = Interaction multiplication between receipt of funds with Firm Size

X₂*Z = Interaction multiplication between Return On assets and Firm Size

X₃*Z = Interaction multiplication between Wadiah Bonus with Firm Size

e_i = Error

Research result

Analysis descriptive

Table 1. Descriptive statistics

	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃	Y	Z
Mean	25082.01	0.8354	27378.27	26	16.65104
Maximum	669879.0	4.08	558636.0	149.58	19.58000
Minimum	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	10.16	14.12000
Std. Dev.	87500.44	1.182268	64369.17	18.96131	1.474160
Observations	115	115	115	115	115

Based on table 1, can is known that amount sample study are 115 samples at 5 Sharia Banks (Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah) 2018Q1-2023Q3. On variables Receipt of ziswaf funds (X₁) based on results statistics descriptive information contained in Table 1 can be is known that variable Receipt of ziswaf funds own average value 25082.01, maximum value 669879.0, minimum value 0.000000 and standard deviation 87500.44.

The variable Return on assets (X₂) is based on results statistics The descriptive descriptions contained in Table 1 can be is known that the Return on Assets variable has average value 0.8354, maximum value 4.08, minimum value 0.000000 and standard deviation 1.182268.

On the Wadiah Bonus variable (X₃) based on results statistics The descriptive descriptions contained in Table 1 can be is known that Wadiah Bonus variables have average value 27378.27, maximum value 558636.0, value minimum 0.000000 and standard deviation 64369.17.

On variables Firm Size (Z) moderation based on results statistics The descriptive descriptions contained in Table 1 can be is known that variable Firm Size moderation has average value 16.65104, maximum value 19.58000, minimum value 14.12000 and standard deviation 1.474160.

ratio (Y) variable is based on results statistics The descriptive descriptions contained in Table 1 can be is known that variable Receipt of Ziswaf Funds own average value 26, maximum value 149.58, minimum value 10, 16 and standard deviation 18.96131.

Election panel data regression

The selection of the panel data regression model is stages analysis For determine method

best between Common Effect, Fixed Effect or Random Effect

1. Test Chow

This test was carried out to find out the best model between the Common Effect Model (CEM) and the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

Table 2. Chow test

Effects Test	Statistics	df	Prob.
Source: Cross-section F	12.83774	(4,106)	0.0000
<i>Eviews</i> (Data processed by the author) Chi-square cross-section	30.416868	4	0.0000

Based on table 2, the results of the Chow test show that the cross-section chi-square probability value is $0.0000 < 0.05$. So it can be said that in this test, the best model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM).

2. Hausman test

This Hausman test aims to select the best model between the Fixed Effect Model (FEM) and the Random Effect Model (REM).

Table 3. Hausman Test Results

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test
Equation: Untitled
Cross-section random effects test

Source: (Data processed by the author)	Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistics	Chi-Sq. df	Prob.
	Random cross-section	54.34483	3	0.0000

From table 3 above, it can be seen that the results of the Hausman test show a probability value of $0.0000 < 0.05$. So it can be said that in this test, the best model to use is the Fixed Effect Model (FEM)

Test Assumptions classic

1. Normality test

Table 4. Normality Test

Series: Residuals	
Sample 1 23	
Observations 23	
Mean	-7.63e-12
Median	-212.3430
Maximum	4224.046
Minimum	-3297.393
Std. Dev.	2234.936
Skewness	0.183739
Kurtosis	1.904999
Jarque-Bera	1.278482
Probability	0.527693

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by the author)

Based on Figure 4 above, it shows that the probability value is 0.527693, which means the probability value is above 0.05 ($0.527693 > 0.05$). So it can be concluded that the data in this study is normally distributed.

2. Multicollinearity test

Table 5. Multicollinearity test

	X ₁	X ₂	X ₃
X ₁	1,000000	0.034521	0.367353
X ₂	0.032459	1,000000	0.464378
X ₃	0.026435	0.426433	1,000000

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 5, the results of the multicollinearity test can be seen if the correlation values between the independent variables are all below 0.85. This means that if the research data does not contain multicollinearity between independent variables.

3. Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 6. Heteroscedasticity Test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
X ₁	-0.004341	0.004917	-0.882817	0.3884
X ₂	63.10679	104.8350	0.601963	0.5543
X ₃	-0.001706	0.003214	-0.530934	0.6016

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by the author)

Based on table 7, the results of the heteroscedasticity test show that the resulting probability values are 2 variables that have values above 0.05 and one other variable below 0.05. A regression model is said to be free from heteroscedasticity if it has a probability value above 0.05. So it can be concluded that in the regression model used in this research there is no heteroscedasticity.

Analysis Panel Data Regression

The following is a panel data regression analysis using the best model, namely the Fixed Effect Model regression:

Table 7. Analysis *Fixed Effect* Panel Data Regression model

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	-120202.7	253902.3	-3.445388	0.0000
X ₁	2407.537	2453.011	1.043056	0.2463
X ₂	0.542365	0.456493	4.45345	0.7547
X ₃	0.053508	0.574536	-0.84543	0.4436
Z	35355.29	15646.70	4.453492	0.0000

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by the author)

Moderated Regression Analysis (MRA)

Moderating variables can be interpreted as variables that can strengthen or weaken

the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The following are the test results from the moderation regression analysis:

Table 8. Analysis test regression moderation

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
C	-334558.3	35345.5	-2.456453	0.0013
X1	6434.345	45634.23	0.145433	0.5124
X2	-13.03455	4.34234	-2.23425	0.0012
X3	4.45345	1.34522	2.46567	0.0154
Z	34543.34	13425.54	2.64544	0.0004
X1Z	-243.3454	2678.675	-0.34454	0.6542
X2Z	0.67854	0.37535	3.45434	0.0012
X3Z	-0.785643	0.345456	-2.75654	0.0157

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by the author)

Statistic test

1. T test

T test, for test is in a way Partial variable dependent have a significant effect on variable independent. Apart from that, it is also used For know is the influence of each variable independent to variable dependent tested at a significance level of 0.05 or with level 95% confidence and rate 5% error.

Table 9. T test

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistics	Prob.
	-			0.0016
C	233435.7	335244.4	-3.352576	
X1	2365.456	45644.10	0.134676	0.8345
X2	-12.35323	2.125256	-3.135433	0.0013
X3	4.363654	1.235476	2.326435	0.0134
Z	42355.65	23563.45	3.454536	0.0004
	-			
X1Z	261.7342	2544.456	-0.135645	0.4535
X2Z	0.463522	0.573134	3.356445	0.0014
	-			
X3Z	0.432532	0.352352	-2.856433	0.0145

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by the author)

Based on the t test (partial). done author on the study This can is known that the results obtained from the t test ie as following:

- 1) Hypothesis 1 (H1): Receipt of ziswaf funds own influence to the Capital Adequacy Ratio. With mark coefficient 45644.10 and value probability 0.8345 which means more big from mark significant 0.05 or 5%. That matter show that Receipt of ziswaf funds influential on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.
- 2) Hypothesis 2 (H2): Return on assets has influence to the Capital adequacy ratio. With

mark coefficient 2.125256 and value probability 0.0013 which means more big from mark significant 0.05 or 5%. That matter show that Return on Assets has an effect on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

3) Hypothesis 3 (H3): Bous Wadiah has influence to the Capital adequacy ratio. With mark coefficient 1.235476 and value probability 0.0134 which means more small from mark significant 0.05 or 5%. That matter show that the Wadiah Bonus has an effect on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

4) Hypothesis 4 (H4): Receipt of ziswaf funds influential the Capital adequacy ratio is moderated by Firm Size. With mark coefficient 2544.456 and value probability 0.4535 which means more big from mark significant 0.05 or 5%. That matter show that Firm Size does not capable moderate influence receipt of ziswaf funds on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

5) Hypothesis 5 (H5): Return on assets has an effect the Capital adequacy ratio is moderated by Firm Size. With mark coefficient 0.573134 and value probability 0.0014 which means more small from mark significant 0.05 or 5%. That matter show that Firm Size is capable moderate the influence of Return on assets on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

6) Hypothesis 6 (H6): Wadiah Bonus has an effect the Capital adequacy ratio is moderated by Firm Size. With mark coefficient 0.352352 and value probability 0.0145 which means more small from mark significant 0.05 or 5%. That matter show that Firm Size is capable moderate The influence of the Wadiah Bonus on the Capital adequacy ratio at Bank Muamalat, Bank Syariah Indonesia, Bank Victoria Syariah, Bank Mega Syariah and Bank Panin Dubai Syariah for the period 2018 Q1-2023 Q3.

7)

2. F test

F test, used For test is in a way simultaneous variable independent influential significant to variable dependent. Following is F test results.

Table 10. F Test Results

	0.00000
Prob(F-statistic)	0

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by the author)

F test in research This use mark significance 0.05 or 5% with criteria If mark significance $F < 0.05$ then coefficient recession worthy used. F test results in table 10 above show mark F significance is 0.000000, value the more small from mark significance namely 0.05. So that it can concluded that Receipt of ziswaf funds, Return on assets. Prize bonus in a way simultaneous own influence to the Capital adequacy ratio.

3. Coefficient Test Determination

Coefficient Determination, used For show how much big contribution independent variable in the regression model in explain variation from variable dependent.

Table 11. Coefficient test results determination

Adjusted R-squared	0.236463
--------------------	----------

Source: *Eviews* (Data processed by the author)

Based on Table 11 panel data regression test results on Capital adequacy ratio as variable dependent, shows that Adjusted R² value is 0.236463. This matter can interpreted that of 23.64% the Capital adequacy ratio variable can be explained by Receipt of ziswaf funds, Return on assets, and wadiah bonus. Whereas the rest can explained with other variables outside the regression model

DISCUSSION

Influence receipt of ziswaf funds to the capital adequacy ratio

Based on table 9 results testing show mark probability Receipt of ziswaf funds equal to 0.8345 which means more big from 0.05. The test results also show direction positive with mark coefficient 2365.456 and t-statistic 0.134676. So that show that receipt of ziswaf funds No own significant influence to the Capital adequacy ratio. So the hypothesis is proposed researcher namely H₁: Effect of Gross NPF on Acceptance of ZISWAF Funds rejected.

Research result This in line with study previously conducted by Muharramah (2017) which shows that receipt of ZISWAF funds is not own influence significant against CAR. This matter because Islamic banking is in use of more capital be careful and focused guard bank liquidity, so No there is influence significant against CAR a approach efficiency and success economy company can used For determine connection between receipt of zakat funds (Zakat) and Return on Assets (ROA).

Effect of Return on assets on Capital adequacy ratio

Based on table 9 results testing show mark the probability of Return on assets is 0.0013, which means more small from 0.05. The test results also show direction negative with mark coefficient -12.35323 and t-statistic -3.135433. So that show that Return on assets has an effect negative to the Capital adequacy ratio. So the hypothesis is proposed researcher namely H₂: The influence of Return on assets on the Capital adequacy ratio is accepted.

Research result In line with research previously conducted by Kurniasari (2022) that ROA has influence positive and significant against CAR. The more high ROA, then the more high CAR. ROA can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR.

The effect of gift bonuses to the capital adequacy ratio

Based on table 9 results testing show mark the probability of the Wadiah Bonus is 0.0134 which means more small from 0.05. The test results also show direction positive with mark coefficient 4.363654 and t-statistic 2.326435. So that show that the Wadiah Bonus has an effect positive to the Capital adequacy ratio. So the hypothesis is proposed researcher namely H₃: The influence of the Wadiah Bonus on the Capital adequacy ratio is accepted.

Research result in line with study previously conducted by Zumara (2021) that gift bonus own influence positive against CAR. Prize bonus can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR.

Influence receipt of ziswaf funds to Capital adequacy ratio Moderated with the capital adequacy ratio

Based on table 9 results testing show mark probability interaction between Receipt of ziswaf funds with profitability equal to 0.4535 which means more big from 0.05. The test results also show direction negative with mark coefficient -261.7342 and t-statistic -0.135645. These results show that Firm Size does not can strengthen influence between Receipt of ziswaf funds with Firm size. So the hypothesis is proposed researcher namely H4: Firm Size is capable moderate receipt of ziswaf funds on the capital adequacy ratio is rejected.

Research result This No in line with study previously conducted by Sardiana & Zulfison (2016) that ZISWAF fund receipts have influence positive against CAR, however influence the can vary depending on size company. ZISWAF funds can be received increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR. However, size company can influence influence the with method reduce deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can lower CAR.

The influence of return on assets on the capital adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size

Based on table 9 results testing show mark probability interaction between Return on assets and profitability of 0.0014 which means more small from 0.05. The test results also show direction positive with mark coefficient 0.463522 and t-statistic 3.356445. These results show that Firm Size can strengthen influence between Income Mudharabah with Firm size. So the hypothesis is proposed researcher namely H5: Firm Size is capable moderate Income Mudharabah to Acceptance of ZISWAF Funds accepted.

Research result This in line with study Previously conducted by Novrianti (2021) that ROA has influence positive against CAR, however influence the can vary depending on size company. ROA can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR. However, size company can influence influence the with method reduce deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can lower CAR.

The effect of gift bonuses on the capital adequacy ratio is moderated with firm size

Based on table 9 results testing show mark probability interaction between the Wadiah Bonus and profitability of 0.0145 which means more small from 0.05. The test results also show direction positive with mark coefficient -0.432532 and t-statistic -2.856433. These results show that Firm Size can strengthen influence between Wadiah Bonus and Firm size. So the hypothesis is proposed researcher namely H6: Firm Size is capable moderate bonuses wadiah to the Capital adequacy ratio is accepted.

Research result This in line with study previously carried out by Mulyadhi (2020) that the wadiah bonus own influence positive against CAR, however influence the can vary depending on size company. Prize bonus can increase deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can increase CAR. However, size company can influence influence the with method reduce deep banking capabilities withhold loss and fulfill obligation finances, so can lower CAR.

Influence Receipt of ziswaf funds, Return on assets, and wadiah bonuses in a way simultaneous to the Capital adequacy ratio

Based on calculations in table 10 can be concluded that variable Receipt of ziswaf funds, Return on assets, and Wadiah Bonus have an influence significant to the capital adequacy ratio. This matter caused Because mark significance $0.000000 < 0.05$. These

results show that Receipt of ziswaf funds, Return on assets, and Wadiah Bonus have an influence in a way simultaneous to Capital adequacy ratio. So the hypothesis is proposed researcher namely H7: Gross NPF, Income Mudharabah, and Wadiah Bonus simultaneous to Acceptance of ZISWAF Funds accepted. On coefficients determination or R Square results value 0.236463. Interpretation from number the show that contribution influence from fourth variable free the is amounting to 23.64% and the remainder namely 76.36% influenced by factors other so that For do study furthermore can use variable independent other (Ramadhani, Sukardi, et al., 2022) (Murniyasih et al., 2022) (Ramadhani, Wahyuningsih, et al., 2022) (Ramadhani et al., 2024).

CONCLUSION

Research result This show that Receipt of ziswaf funds affect CAR significantly significant. which mean that if mark Reception increase then CAR will decrease low, and vice versa. In other words, Return on assets has impact significant negative to CAR; if return on assets is generated high, that is will produce CAR decreases, and vice versa. Next, during interaction variable moderation, Firm size is not can control influence a Receipt of ziswaf funds on sector CAR finances in 2018–2023. Additionally, firm size does not can control the influence of return on assets on mark company sector finances in 2018–2023.

REFERENCES

- Agustina, I. D., Wahidiyah, R. 'Aini, Misbahuddin, A. A., Ningtyas, M. N., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2024). MSMEs Interest in the Use of Sharia E-Payment: Expanded Implementation of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). *Jurnal Ilmiah Bisnis Dan Ekonomi Asia*, 18(1), 71–86. <https://doi.org/10.32815/jibeka.v18i1.1905>
- Arkaan, D. U., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2024). Does Financial Ratio Have an Impact on The Growth of Sharia Banking in The World. *Tabarru': Islamic Banking and Finance*, 7(1), 299–309. [https://doi.org/10.25299/jtb.2024.vol7\(1\).16248](https://doi.org/10.25299/jtb.2024.vol7(1).16248)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022a). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/jebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022b). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023a). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023b). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Operasional pada Industri Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ekonomi Islam*, 14(2), 158–174. <https://doi.org/10.22236/jei.v14i2.11121>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023c). Pemetaan Penelitian Risiko Reputasi pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023d). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan

- Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023e). Research Mapping on Credit Risk in Islamic and Conventional Banking. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023a). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023b). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAFTA (Journal of Accounting, Finance, Taxation & Auditing)*, 4(2), 32–53. <https://doi.org/10.28932/jafta.v4i2.7650>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023c). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023d). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of Research in Management)*, 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023e). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023f). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio On Investment (ROI) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023g). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Total Asset Turnover (TATO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Manajemen*, 20(2), 40–53. <https://doi.org/10.36406/jam.v20i2.975>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023h). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023i). Research Mapping of Working Capital Turnover (WCT) Ratio in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Vosviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Global Financial Accounting Journal*,

- 7(2), 181–194. <https://doi.org/10.37253/gfa.v7i2.7709>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syar Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). The Effect of Knowledge, Trust, Products, Services and Religiosity on Interest in Saving. *The 9th International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business (ICONIES 2023)*, 85–96. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037033>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Equity (ROE) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Murniyasih, E., Wahyuningsih, P., & Ramadhani, S. F. (2022). Design of Peatland Monitoring System Based on Wireless Sensor Network. *Electro Luceat*, 8(1), 93–99. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.32531/jelekn.v8i1.454>
- Ramadhani, S. F., Sukardi, S., Romadhona, A., Wahyuningsih, P., & Fitianingsih, D. (2022). Public Service Evaluation Information System At Puskesmas Tinggede Using Community Satisfaction Index Method. *Electro Luceat*, 8(1), 118–124. <https://doi.org/doi.org/10.32531/jelekn.v8i1.467>
- Ramadhani, S. F., Wahyuningsih, P., Jalil, A., & Suryana, S. (2022). Design of digital kWh-Meter to top-up the electric pulse by automatically using Relay Module Based on SMS and Arduino Uno. *ILKOM Jurnal Ilmiah*, 14(3), 229–236. <https://doi.org/10.33096/ilkom.v14i3.1221.229-236>
- Ramadhani, S. F., Wahyuningsih, P., & Mahka, M. F. R. (2024). Penerapan Metode Waterfall dalam Monitoring Perkara Perceraian dengan Dampungan Pengacara pada Pengadilan Agama Toli-Toli. *INFOMATEK: Jurnal Informatika, Manajemen Dan Teknologi*, 26(1), 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.23969/infomatek.v26i1.8022>
- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Maybank Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan, Vol 5, No 1 (2023):*

JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>

- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Sasongko, D. F., Budianto, E. W. H., Arkaan, D. U., & Herawati, A. (2024). Internalisasi Nilai Moderasi Beragama Dalam Sistem Ekonomi Syariah Pada UMKM Halal Melalui Produk Pembiayaan Syariah. *Martabe: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 7(4), 1303–1320. <https://doi.org/10.31604/jpm.v7i4.1303-1320>
- Setiani, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Retnasih, N. R. (2024). Implementation of Integrated Online System (IOS) in Improving Learning Capability Based on Technology Management. *Educate: Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan (JTP)*, 9(1), 44–56. <https://doi.org/10.24114/jtp.v8i2.3329>
- Susanto, R. M., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Pasar Modal Syariah. *At-Tasyri': Jurnal Ilmiah Prodi Hukum Ekonomi Syariah*, 15(2), 167–185. <https://doi.org/10.47498/tasyri.v15i2.1759>